

The analysis of participants in citizen science project

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Abstract

Citizen science involves citizens engaging in research activities in collaboration with researchers, or on their own. It includes activities ranging from collecting everyday data to developing research plans and analysing data. By involving citizens in these research activities, it is possible to increase their contact with science and technology.

When considering ways to engage the public with science and technology issues, many people frequently consider activities such as visiting science museums, watching science programs on TV or reading books. Indeed, EU data shows that fewer people participate in citizen science projects than those who use science museums, science television programs or books. However, the current low participation in citizen science suggests potential for future growth. If citizen science were more widespread, more people would be able to engage with science and technology issues.

This study explores whether there are barriers to participation in order to increase the number of people taking part in citizen science. Specifically, this study investigated the profiles of citizen science participants to consider whether participants were skewed towards individuals sharing common characteristics, thereby hindering others from participating.

The research methodology involved combining EU survey data (Eurobarometer 516 and 557) showing the profiles of citizen science participants with general data provided by the OECD and UNESCO. Correlations were then examined using analytical software.

The survey results showed that there were no correlation with the factors that were tested, indicating that all countries have the potential to increase participation in citizen science. It is hoped that specific methods for increasing participation in citizen science will be considered in the future.

1. Introduction

Citizen science projects provide valuable opportunities for people to engage with science and technology issues. By participating in these projects, people can observe scientific phenomena and develop a greater interest in science and technology.

There are many approaches to contact with science and technology such as watching a science programs on TV, reading science books, and visiting science museums, but citizen science projects remain relatively uncommon. Special Eurobarometer 516, *European citizens' knowledge and attitudes towards science and technology* (European Commission, 2021) showed that only 12% of people state that they engage with science and technology by actively taking part in scientific projects (regularly and occasionally), while 69% do so by watching documentaries or reading science and technology-related publications, magazines or books, and 33% do so by visiting science and technology museums. If citizen science were more widespread, more people would be able to engage with science and technology issues.

Citizen science may not be widespread because of barriers to participation. For example, if a citizen science project is dominated by highly educated people, those with lower levels of education may find it difficult to participate. In fact, the EU's *Mutual learning exercise on citizen science initiatives* (European Commission, 2022) showed the importance of higher education as creating the basis for participation in citizen science. For example, In Galaxy Zoo, 65% of participants had tertiary education and 10% had doctoral level degrees. In OpenStreetMap, 78% of participants hold tertiary education, with 8% holding doctoral level degrees. In Transcribe Bentham, 97% of participants have tertiary education and 24% hold doctoral level degrees.

Is it only in certain projects that participants tend to have a high level of education? In addition, are there any other common characteristics among participants besides their educational background? This study explores whether there are barriers to participation in order to increase the number of people taking part in citizen science. Specifically, this study investigated the profiles of citizen science participants to consider whether participants were skewed towards individuals sharing common characteristics, thereby hindering others from participating. This study would enable consideration of how to promote citizen science in the future.

2. Method

2.1 Data

2.1.1 Data on educational background

The research methodology involved combining EU survey data showing the profiles of citizen science participants with general data provided by the OECD and UNESCO. This study used the Eurobarometer 516 and 557 as EU survey data. Special Eurobarometer 516, *European citizens' knowledge and attitudes towards science and technology* (European Commission, 2021) was commissioned by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation and carried out by the Kantar network between 13 April and 10 May 2021. In total, 37,103 respondents from EU and non-EU countries and territories took part in the survey. Three

years later, Special Eurobarometer 557, *European citizens' knowledge and attitudes towards science and technology* (European Commission, 2024) was also commissioned by the European Commission, Directorate General for Research and Innovation and carried out by Verian Brussels (formerly Kantar Public) in the 27 EU Member States and eight non-EU countries between 12 September and 10 October 2024. A total of 34,207 respondents from different social and demographic groups were interviewed in their mother tongue.

These surveys include a question about actively taking part in scientific project:
 - And now, a few questions on how you engage with science and technology issues.
 Do you: - Actively take part in scientific projects

These surveys also asked about talking about science and technology-related issues with family or friends, visiting science and technology museums, and so on, but the above question was considered to be related to the citizen science project, so this study analysed the answers to the question.

As shown in the table 1, the answer to the question was also categorized by age at the end of education in Eurobarometer, and there seems to be a correlation between project participants and the age at which education ends. The older people are at the end of their education, the higher the percentage of people who have participated in citizen science is, especially the percentage of those who actively take part in scientific projects.

Regarding the tertiary education rates by country, this study used the data of OECD or Eurostat. The data of the ratio for tertiary education students and doctoral or equivalent students was compiled by OECD in 2023, and the data of the number for tertiary education students and doctoral or equivalent students was compiled by Eurostat in 2023. This study analyses whether factors that seem to be correlated overall also show correlations when examined by country, combining several datasets.

Table 1. The data of Eurobarometer 516 (Actively take part in scientific projects – End of Education)

	End of Education			
	15-	16-19	20+	Still studying
Total 'Yes'	140	902	1,533	626
	(4%)	(9%)	(16%)	(22%)
Total 'Hardly ever / no'	3,031	9,336	8,220	2,154
	(95%)	(90%)	(84%)	(77%)

2.1.2 Data on research work

This study also looked into whether there were other factors that correlated with participation in citizen science projects. There were the data of Eurobarometer 516 that showed whether people in following four categories participated in citizen science projects.

- Worked in research / science / innovative technology development
- Both you and a family member do or did in the past.
 - You alone do or did in the past.
 - A family member does or did in the past.

(d) No

As shown in the table 2, there seems to be a correlation between citizen science project participants and researchers in science and technology. It is shown that people who are personally or family members involved in science and technology are more likely to participate in citizen science.

The people who involved in science and technology by country are shown in the data of human resources in science and technology, which is compiled by Eurostat in 2024. It shows both the data of people working in an S&T occupation and those who have a tertiary education and work in an S&T occupation. This study explores whether there is a correlation between these two datasets.

Table 2. The data of Eurobarometer 516 (Actively take part in scientific projects – Worked in research / science / innovative technology development)

	Worked in research / science / innovative technology development			
	Both you and a family member do or did in the past.	You alone do or did in the past.	A family member does or did in the past.	No.
Total 'Yes'	146 (49%)	672 (40%)	525 (21%)	1,947 (9%)
Total 'Hardly ever / no'	153 (51%)	1016 (60%)	1884 (78%)	20,258 (90%)

2.1.3 Data on economic scale

This study also investigated the data of Eurobarometer 516 showing whether people who identify as belonging to each of the following classes participated in citizen science projects.

Consider belonging to

- (a) The working class
- (b) The lower middle class
- (c) The middle class
- (d) The upper middle class
- (e) The higher class of society

As shown in the table 3, there seems to be a correlation between citizen science project participants and high social class. It is shown that the higher the social class, the greater the financial resources, and the more people seem to participate in citizen science projects.

The data showing each country's economic capacity can be seen by looking at the GNI, Per Capita GNI (US Dollars), which is compiled by United Nations in 2023. This study also combines and analyses these data.

Table 3. The data of Eurobarometer 516 (Actively take part in scientific projects – Consider belonging to)

	Consider belonging to				
	The working class	The lower middle class	The middle class	The upper middle class	The higher class of society
Total 'Yes'	311 (6%)	345 (9%)	1920 (13%)	615 (23%)	69 (29%)
Total 'Hardly ever / no'	4908 (93%)	3569 (90%)	12273 (86%)	2091 (77%)	170 (71%)

2.1.4 Data on internet usage rates

Finally, this study examined data showing the relationship between frequency of internet usage and participation in citizen science projects.

- Use of the Internet
- (a) Everyday
 - (b) Often / Sometimes
 - (c) Never

As shown in the table 4, there seems to be a correlation between citizen science project participants and use of the Internet. It is shown that the higher the internet usage rate, the greater the participation in citizen science projects.

The data on internet usage rates by country can be found in ICT statistics “Individuals using the Internet” compiled by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) in 2023. This study also combines and analyses these data.

Table 4. The data of Eurobarometer 516 (Actively take part in scientific projects – Use of the Internet)

	Use of the Internet		
	Everyday	Often / Sometimes	Never
Total 'Yes'	3014 (14%)	172 (9%)	98 (4%)
Total 'Hardly ever / no'	19039 (86%)	1677 (89%)	2153 (95%)

2.2 Method

In order to investigate the relationship between project participants and other factors, this study used the JMP student edition 19 (SAS Institute Inc.). Through the JMP, this study examined the correlation coefficient between two factors by simple regression analyses and analysed whether a correlation existed.

3. Results

3.1 The relationship with educational background

3.1.1 The relationship between the ratio of project participants and tertiary education or doctoral education

This analysis looked at the relationship between the ratio of project participants and tertiary education students using the data of Eurobarometer 516 and OECD. Figure 1 plots the percentage of citizen science project participants and the ratio of tertiary education students or doctoral students in 2021 and 2024. According to this figure, there seems to be no correlation between experience of citizen science participation and educational background.

Figure 1. The relationship between the ratio of project participants and tertiary education or doctoral education

A. Austria,	B. Belgium,	C. Czechia,	D. Denmark,	E. Estonia,	F. Finland,	G. France,
H. Germany,	I. Greece,	J. Hungary,	K. Iceland,	L. Ireland,	M. Italy,	N. Latvia,
O. Lithuania,	P. Luxembourg,	Q. Netherlands,	R. Norway,	S. Poland,	T. Portugal,	U. Slovakia,
V. Slovenia,	W. Spain,	X. Sweden,	Y. Switzerland,	Z. Türkiye,	a. United Kingdom	

The ratio of project participants in 2021 and tertiary education (p value = 0.71)

The ratio of project participants in 2021 and doctoral education (p value = 0.97)

3.1.2 The relationship between the number of project participants and tertiary education students

This analysis looked at the relationship between the number of project participants and tertiary education students using the data of Eurobarometer 516 and Eurostat. Figure 2 plots the number of citizen science project participants and the number of tertiary education students or doctoral students. According to this figure, there also seems to be no correlation between experience of citizen science participation and educational background. Even when comparing this data, the only thing that can be seen is that Turkey has a particularly high number of participants in citizen science projects in 2021, and Netherlands has a particularly high number of participants in citizen science projects in 2024.

Figure 2. The relationship between the number of project participants and tertiary education or doctoral education

A. Albania,	B. Austria,	C. Belgium,	D. Bosnia and Herzegovina,	E. Bulgaria,	F. Croatia,
G. Cyprus,	H. Czechia,	I. Denmark,	J. Estonia,	K. Finland,	L. France,
M. Germany,	N. Greece,	O. Hungary,	P. Iceland,	Q. Ireland,	R. Italy,
S. Latvia,	T. Lithuania,	U. Luxembourg,	V. Malta,	W. Montenegro,	X. Netherlands,
Y. North Macedonia,	Z. Norway,	a. Poland,	b. Portugal,	c. Romania,	d. Serbia,
e. Slovakia,	f. Slovenia,	g. Spain,	h. Sweden,	i. Switzerland,	j. Türkiye

The number of project participants in 2021 and tertiary education (p value = 0.002) The number of project participants in 2021 and doctoral education (p value = 0.022)

The number of project participants in 2024 and tertiary education (p value = 0.029) The number of project participants in 2024 and doctoral education (p value = 0.24)

3.2 The relationship with research work

Figure 3 and 4 shows the relationship between experience of citizen science participation and ratio/number of researchers in science and technology in 2021 and 2024. However, there also seems to be no correlation. The fact that can be seen is that Turkey has a particularly high ratio of participants in citizen science projects in 2021, and Montenegro has a particularly high ratio of participants in citizen science projects in 2024.

Figure 3. The relationship between the ratio of citizen science project participants and researchers / researchers with tertiary education in science and technology

A. Albania, B. Belgium, C. Bulgaria, D. Croatia, E. Cyprus, F. Czechia, G. Denmark, H. Estonia, I. Finland, J. France, K. Germany, L. Greece, M. Hungary, N. Iceland, O. Ireland, P. Italy, Q. Latvia, R. Lithuania, S. Luxembourg, T. Malta, U. Montenegro, V. Netherlands, W. North Macedonia, X. Norway, Y. Poland, Z. Portugal, a. Romania, b. Serbia, c. Slovakia, d. Slovenia, e. Spain, f. Sweden, g. Switzerland, h. Türkiye

The ratio of project participants in 2021 and researchers (p value = 0.51)

The ratio of project participants in 2021 and researchers with tertiary education (p value = 0.47)

The ratio of project participants in 2024 and researchers (p value = 0.60)

The ratio of project participants in 2024 and researchers with tertiary education (p value = 0.74)

Figure 4. The relationship between the number of citizen science project participants and researchers / researchers with tertiary education in science and technology in 2021 and 2024

A. Albania, B. Belgium, C. Bosnia and Herzegovina, D. Bulgaria, E. Croatia, F. Cyprus, G. Czechia, H. Denmark, I. Estonia, J. Finland, K. France, L. Germany, M. Greece, N. Hungary, O. Iceland, P. Ireland, Q. Italy, R. Latvia, S. Lithuania, T. Luxembourg, U. Malta, V. Netherlands, W. North Macedonia, X. Norway, Y. Poland, Z. Portugal, a. Romania, b. Serbia, c. Slovakia, d. Slovenia, e. Spain, f. Sweden, g. Switzerland, h. Türkiye

The number of project participants in 2021 and researchers
(p value = 0.29)

The number of project participants in 2024 and researchers
(p value = 0.24)

3.3 The relationship with economic scale and Internet usage rates

Figure 5 shows the relationship between experience of citizen science participation and per capita GNI / individuals using the Internet. However, there also seems to be no correlation between the participation in citizen science and economic scale or Internet usage rates.

Figure 5. The relationship between the ratio of citizen science project participants and per capita GNI / individuals using the Internet

A. Albania, B. Austria, C. Belgium, D. Bosnia and Herzegovina, E. Bulgaria, F. Croatia, G. Cyprus, H. Czechia, I. Denmark, J. Estonia, K. Finland, L. France, M. Germany, N. Greece, O. Hungary, P. Iceland, Q. Ireland, R. Italy, S. Latvia, T. Lithuania, U. Luxembourg, V. Malta, W. Montenegro, X. Netherlands, Y. North Macedonia, Z. Norway, a. Poland, b. Portugal, c. Romania, d. Serbia, e. Slovakia, f. Slovenia, g. Spain, h. Sweden, i. Switzerland, j. Türkiye, k. United Kingdom

The ratio of project participants in 2021 and per capita GNI (p value = 0.20)

The ratio of project participants in 2024 and per capita GNI (p value = 0.078)

The ratio of project participants in 2021 and individuals using the Internet (p value = 0.20)

The ratio of project participants in 2024 and individuals using the Internet (p value = 0.006)

4. Discussion

While the EU survey data showed that the profile of citizen science participants across the EU is more likely to be highly educated, work in science and technology, come from higher social classes, and use the internet frequently, this study found no common factors were identified among nations with high levels of participation in citizen science. Specifically, no correlation was found between the high number/proportion of participants in citizen science and the number/proportion of highly educated people, the number/proportion of researchers, national economic scale and Internet usage rates.

In other words, when explored by country, it is not true that the more people with higher education, the more likely they are to participate in citizen science projects by country. Some countries (such as Turkey, Netherlands and Montenegro) have a high participation in citizen science projects participation even when the number/ratio of people with higher education is small. Similarly, there is no evidence that countries with a large number of researchers, a large economic scale, and a high internet usage rate tend to have a higher participation rate in citizen science projects.

Therefore, it was shown that all countries have the potential to increase participation in citizen science even in countries with fewer highly educated people or researchers, and with a smaller national economy or lower internet penetration rate. The opportunities are available for everyone to participate in citizen science.

In this way, this research showed that these factors are not the most significant for willingness to participate in citizen science projects, so if there was some incentive, people might participate in them. Therefore, further research is needed to consider what incentives might encourage people to participate in citizen science.

5. References

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